

Exploring Education Access, Opportunities, and Massification in Higher Education in Uganda

Kidega Charles¹, Haufiku Gottlieb Ndambo Djaya², Mintamir Shegaw Taye³,
Olusegun Adeola Olubunmi⁴, Awila George⁵, Chiremba Eunifer⁶, Wakshuma
Dime Rare⁷, Thet Khaing⁸

¹Zhejiang Normal University, College of Education, China

Abstract: This paper explores the concepts of education access, opportunities, and massification in higher education in Uganda by examining the importance of providing equal access to education for individuals from diverse backgrounds. The discussion delves into the various barriers that hinder educational access, including socioeconomic factors, gender disparities, and geographical limitations. It explores the role of scholarships, grants, and financial aid in promoting educational opportunities for underprivileged and marginalized groups. Additionally, it emphasizes the need for educational institutions to develop inclusive policies that cater to the unique needs and aspirations of students from diverse backgrounds. It analyzes the challenges and opportunities presented by the growing number of students seeking higher education. The study employed qualitative research based on a literature review and analyzed using themes. The paper examines how massification affects educational quality, resources, and infrastructure, as well as the implications for equity and inclusivity, and explores strategies that can be adopted to address the challenges associated with massification while maintaining educational standards and quality. It discusses the importance of enhancing institutional capacities, expanding infrastructure, and embracing innovative teaching and learning methods. Overall, this paper comprehensively explains the complexities surrounding education access, opportunities, and massification in higher education. It offers insights into the measures required to ensure equitable access, foster opportunities for all, and effectively manage the growing demands for higher education.

Keywords: Education Access and opportunities, Massification and Higher Education, Uganda

*Corresponding Author: Kidega Charles, Prof. Zheng Song, Haufiku Gottlieb Ndambo Djaya, Mintamir Shegaw Taye, Olusegun Adeola Olubunmi, Wakshuma Dime Rare, Awila George, Chiremba Eunifer, Thet Khaing

Accepted: 25 November, 2023; **Published:** 10 December, 2023

How to cite this article: Kidega Charles, Haufiku Gottlieb Ndambo Djaya, Mintamir Shegaw Taye, Olusegun Adeola Olubunmi, Awila George, Wakshuma Dime Rare, Chiremba Eunifer, Thet Khaing (2023), *Exploring Education access, Opportunities, and Massification in Higher Education in Uganda*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(11), 70-86. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10371455>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/images and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. The author (s) is fully responsible for the text, figure, and data in this manuscript submitted for possible open-access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

One of the most important concepts for welfare consideration and development is the distribution of education (Thomas et al., 2001). To overcome poverty, both individual and community productivity depend on fairness and equality in the distribution of educational opportunities. The World Bank claims that when people's abilities are evenly distributed, then disparities in the educational attainment of the population as a whole result in large welfare losses (Dworkin, 2021). It is commonly known that equitable access to education promotes welfare and development. Parity in the allocation of educational opportunities results in parity in the allocation of health benefits. In addition to increasing the potential for household income growth and national development, it empowers women and girls (Amutuhaire, 2023). A ripple effect of social mobility that affects one generation after another benefits the entire country when there is equity and gender, equality in access and distribution of quality education. Distribution of education is also a vital lever for achieving other development goals. In particular, goal 1 is poverty eradication; Goal 4 is quality education; Goal 5 is gender equality; Goal 8 is decent work and economic growth; Goal 10 is reduced inequality; Goal 13 is climate action; and Goal sixteen and peace, justice, and strong institutions, respectively all greatly benefit from it. Therefore, a key component of any nation's development plan needs to be the distribution of education fairly. Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has the lowest rate of higher education access worldwide, with gender disparities and critical equity prevailing both within and between countries. While the average enrollment rate for men and women worldwide was 19% in 1990 and 26% in 2000, access was only roughly 5% in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) according to Ver spoor (2020), compared to over 70% in highly industrialized (OECD) nations. Of course, those who claim that things in Africa are considerably better now than they were in the past are correct. The current percentages for Africa have doubled from 2.4% in 1990. The examples given by the African Development Bank (AFDB, 2018) suggest in its 2018 report that the issue of poverty and inequality is not due to a lack of resources per se, but rather to how resources are managed, specifically the absence or lack of the idea of equity in the practices, systems, and policies in charge of allocating them. Inclusion is promoted by (Deutsch et al., 2020) as a solution to disparities that are sustained by internationalization. For example, in East Africa, women are not given the same priority as men when it comes to accessing higher education, even with the various internationalization strategies in place. In 2018, women's regional gross enrollment ratio was 8%, while men's was 10% (UNESCO, 2022). By the end of the 1990s, more people had access to higher education. acknowledged as the primary instrument for resolving social injustices and advancing development. Consequently, the United Nations (UN) established universal access to high-quality education as the cornerstone of both the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) of 2000 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of 2015. The UN promises to " 2030 ensure equal access for all women and men to affordable quality technical, vocational, and tertiary education, including university" as part of the SDG framework. UN, 2015). This is consistent with the 1948 United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which says that "all individuals shall have equal access to higher education based only on merit." The 1976 United Nations International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (UDHR, 2011) pledges to provide equal access to postsecondary education "by every appropriate means, based on capacity, and in particular by the progressive introduction of free education" (Article 13 2c, UN 1976). It is argued that higher education is what ensures that all citizen's educational accomplishments contribute to the welfare and development of the entire society.

This conclusion was drawn in light of studies that demonstrate how regional differences in Uganda's educational opportunities, outcomes, and access have remained stable (Kasirye Ibrahim, 2009). To investigate practices, systems, and policies that might improve opportunities, outcomes, and access to education in Uganda's underserved regions (World Bank, 2006). To address the issue, it is necessary to maintain the progress made in primary education access across the nation by doing away with the dropout phenomenon and significantly raising completion rates of poor transfer from elementary to secondary and post-secondary education levels.

1. Literature Review

(a) Trow's modification model

Model 1 Three levels can be used to summarize Trow's massification model of higher education: elite, mass, and universal (Trow, 2006). Preparing students for elite roles and molding the minds and characters of the ruling class are the two main goals of the elite level of massification of higher education. The transfer of skills and preparation for a wider range of technical and economic roles for economic development is the mass level of massification of higher education. The adaptation of the entire population to the rapid social and technological change of society is the universal level of massification of higher education. According to Marginson (2017), the three stages of massification illustrate how access to higher education changes from being an elite privilege to a mass right and ultimately a universal obligation. According to Shan and Guo (2014), the classification is based on the total number of students or Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) of the relevant age group enrolled in elite, mass, and Universal Higher Education, with the GER falling between 15% and 50%, and rising above 50%. The percentage of a given age group that enrolls in higher education in a given nation is known as the GER. Marginson (2020) emphasized that transitioning from one level of higher education to another does not eliminate the preceding level; that is, mass higher education can exist at the universal higher education level. Creating opportunities for more students to enroll in the same category is known as diversification in higher education (Unangst, 2017). Teichler (1996) asserts that diversification can take two forms: vertical and horizontal. Whereas horizontal diversification refers to the particular knowledge profile, teaching and learning approach, and focus on problem-solving, vertical diversification distinguishes higher education based on quality, reputation, and the potential status of graduates. The goal, internal organizational culture, and governance may also be connected to horizontal diversification. This also results in the introduction of new teaching methods like online learning, remote learning, and the use of new technology to instruct students off-campus at universities or colleges. The concept of differentiation refers to the distinctions made amongst institutions of higher learning according to their objectives. Within and between higher education institutions, differentiation in higher education encompasses both vertical and horizontal differentiation. Whereas the forces of the labor market propel vertical differentiation, access concerns propel horizontal differentiation. Whereas vertical differentiation is centered on the skills and competencies needed in the labor market, horizontal differentiation is based on access and choice to postsecondary education.

(b) Feminist standpoint theory

The theory of resource access is "grounded in historical socio-economic context and varies according to particular Standpoints," according to feminist Standpoint empiricism. According to this theory, some people may be able to benefit from social location and status in terms of having access to resources like public university educational opportunities. epistemic groups; and that an individual's Standpoint social position or geographic location determines their particular epistemic advantage (Intemann, 2010). Gender, district of origin, district population quota, high school, and affirmative action are specific standpoints in Uganda because they each constitute a fundamental component of the standards that govern how public university educational opportunities are distributed. It is hypothesized that each of the aforementioned five components may systematically shape and restrict access to educational opportunities at public universities within the framework of the Standpoint Theory. This theory raises the following query: How do public University educational opportunities in regions, districts, and public University fields of study differ depending on where students attended high school and where they were born in Uganda? In the context of public policies, systems, and practices responsible for the distribution of higher education, what is the role, meaning, and implication of Uganda's districts, population quota, high school graduation rates, gender, and affirmative action as standpoints for access to public university educational opportunities in regions and districts? Affirmative action has been institutionalized in Uganda, as opposed to Kenya, since the National Resistance Movement (NRM) assumed power in 1986. The October 1995 adoption of Uganda's new Constitution included many measures aimed at achieving gender parity and equitable representation

for men and women in all spheres of public life. Affirmative action is permitted under Article 32:1 in favor of marginalized groups (GoU, 1995). The government has put in place a variety of measures to guarantee observance of human rights and men's equal participation. There is now a distinct ministry dedicated to gender, labor, and social development. Empowering communities, especially marginalized groups, to realize and harness their potential for sustainable and gender-responsive development is one of its goals. Universities are being forced to consider options outside of the traditional classroom setting due to the rising number of students who meet the requirements for admission each year. Universities have made their services available to students who are not accepted into their traditional classroom programs through distance education, allowing them to study at home, at work, or even in rural areas. With a few programs, distance learning helped Universities' enrolment rates to reach over 15% of the overall student body on average. Print materials, audio and video cassettes, graphics, and some universities' use of ICT allow students enrolled in distance education programs to study at home or any other location. ICT in distance learning enhances students' access to information and reduces the gap between on- and off-campus learning. ICT is more efficient than traditional classrooms and can serve a large number of students, regardless of where they are in the world. This suggests that students who receive their education remotely have the freedom to manage their education. Compared to traditional classroom programs, distance education offers two main advantages. More students are admitted to distance learning programs than to traditional classroom settings, and this lessens crowding on university grounds. Not all of the accepted students attend the University daily. Once more, distance learning programs give students greater learning flexibility and enable them to finish their courses whenever it suits them. Unlike traditional classroom programs, distance education programs give students more years to study and the freedom to choose the courses they feel they can complete in a given semester. Even the least talented students can complete their academic objectives with the time and freedom provided to distance learners. It is also well known that, when compared to traditional classroom courses, distance education courses are more affordable.

2. Research Methodology

This paper employed a qualitative research approach based on existing literature and data were analyzed on themes and data were collected from key policy documents from both government and private Universities within the country and the National Council for Higher Education (NCHE). Additional information was obtained from research findings conducted by other researchers in the field of higher education. Literature was extensively analyzed to develop an depth understanding of access to higher education and the challenges facing higher education in Uganda, more literature was from Chinese higher education. Data searchers were focused on the key social, economic, and political challenges that have continued to affect most University graduates in the labor market, and why adaptability as well retention in the Ugandan labor market have always been very problematic without any clear evidence. Multiple internet searches were conducted by the use of major search engines like Google Scholar, web Science, and Scopus for additional data mining using key search terms. In addition, the access to education and equity in education and the massification of higher education in Uganda in past years give a clear history of our education. Solutions and recommendations were also given to improve on the key issues in Uganda's higher education.

3. Finding and Discussion

3.1. Key Issues in Higher Education in Uganda

These were important areas that were outlined in the past to give everyone easy access to education, with a focus on women primarily because the majority of them were not enrolled in school. The majority of this initiative is still in operation today, and it has made higher education more accessible.

3.1.1. Affirmative Action

Uganda's education system aims to provide high-quality education to all students. Higher education implemented the Affirmative Action program in 1991 (Sekaggya-Bagarukayo & Oddy, 2022). This gave qualified women an additional

1.5 points toward admission to public universities. Similar worries about the marginalization of students from remote districts and impoverished schools, as well as individuals with disabilities, Talents are to be rewarded through Uganda's higher education distribution system. Additionally, it aims to distribute things equally for men and women. The elimination of discrimination resulting from previous and current policies, systems, and practices is the primary goal of the affirmative action policy. Uganda has an international duty to comply with the United Nations (UN) Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination, which was signed in 1989. To preserve Article 2.2 of the convention and domesticate its application in its national laws, policies, systems, and practices, Uganda has adopted several legislative and policy instruments since 1973. The 1.5 bonus point intervention policy for public university education was implemented in 1991 to improve In 2004, the government will implement a restricted district quota system for admission. women's access to education generally. Article 32 of the Ugandan Constitution was amended in 1995 to include the right to affirmative action. Less than 15% of students admitted to Makerere, Uganda's only public university, were female before the implementation of affirmative action in 1991 (MoES, 2012). For admission to public universities, qualified Ugandan women were granted 1.5 bonus intervention points under the Affirmative Action program. The idea that women in higher education needed to be compensated for structural and historical biases that prevented them from participating in higher education was widely viewed as a mechanism for reparative justice. In 1990, the Senate of Makerere University implemented the 1.5-point program to increase the proportion of female students enrolled in undergraduate programs. Affirmative action has a long history in Uganda when it comes to admitting female students. In 1922, Makerere University was founded as a technical college for men. In 1990, the university implemented the 1.5 points system to boost the enrollment of female students. A 1.5-point bonus was given to female applicants to universities in addition to their exam results. The percentage of female students enrolled at Makerere University increased from 23.9% in 1989–1990 to 45.8% in 2003–2004, and this increase has been linked to the 1.5 scheme. The rise in the percentage of women pupils accepted using the 1.5-point system and how it relates to the gender profile Enhancing the education of girls in Uganda has the potential to break the cycle of poverty within families and possibly the entire nation. A woman's income increases by 10–25 percent for each extra year of education. Ninety percent of this income will then be reinvested in her family by an educated woman. Assisting a girl to finish her education will increase her chances of sending her offspring to school by double.

3.1.2. Gender Inequality and Equity in Uganda

Uganda is home to about 49.17 million people, of whom 51.71% are women. Uganda has committed to a society that is more gender-equal over the last 20 years by encouraging the emancipation of women. Gender norms, the lack of education and skill development among women, and other factors are some of the reasons Ugandan women are marginalized. Organizations can lessen gender disparities while empowering women and assisting them in escaping poverty by enhancing women's education in Uganda.

Fairness, impartiality, justice, and equal opportunity for every student to fully participate in all academic opportunities are all considered aspects of equity in the field of education (Mintz, 2021). Thus, expanding access to international education opportunities for all students and ensuring their success are equally important components of equity in the internationalization of higher education (Almeida, 2018). It concerns the efficacy and efficiency of decisions made at the national institutional level, which is in charge of delivering outcomes and attending to the needs of the populace throughout the nation's districts and regions. Sharing the advantages of resource distribution in a way that is fair and sensitive to the needs of communities and individuals requires openness, transparency, and accountability. Despite the implementation of the Science Policy in 2004 and Affirmative Action in 1991, there are still remarkably few female scientists in Uganda. In secondary schools, there were only 23.6% female teachers. These further disadvantage the girls by leaving gaps in the community of advocates, counselors, and role models. Men made up seventy percent of tertiary students. Seven of the ten women who enrolled in postsecondary education left by year three. Men make up 71.4 percent of the total enrolled in year three, while women make up 28.6%. This is indicative of the high female dropout rates in

BTVET (business, technical, and vocational education and training) institutions. The majority of instructors, 73% of them, are men. This necessitates purposeful actions to advance gender mainstreaming in Uganda's educational system and equal opportunities for men and women (MoES, 2016). Students from underprivileged schools located in remote, impoverished districts of the nation have significantly less access to schools with greater resources due to the widening educational gaps between districts and schools across the nation (Oddy & Sekaggya-Bagarukayo, 2022). This frequently results in disparities in the distribution of educational opportunities at public Universities and significant variations in the quality of education. These elements may muddy the cause and effect of laws like affirmative action and make it more difficult to achieve this assessment's intended goal. In Uganda, gender inequality is still a major problem. These disparities have been made worse by the current COVID-19 pandemic, which has had a major impact on women's education in Uganda. Inequalities in the rates of male and female literacy existed in Uganda even before the pandemic. In 2018, the adult male literacy rate was 83%, while the adult female rate was 71%, according to the World Bank.

3.1.3. Funding of higher education

Access and equity issues are inherent in Uganda's higher education funding structure and have not yet been resolved. Three parties provide funding for higher education in Uganda: the government, parents/students, and international and local philanthropic organizations. All of the trees lack the resources necessary to fully address the issue of increased access, and the current distribution strategies favor children from wealthy households. Private providers are an additional and significant source of postsecondary education; in this scenario, students and their families bear the majority of the educational costs. Before the 1970s, higher education could only be funded by the state. But over the past three decades, the state's portion of the GDP has decreased, both numerically and as a percentage, while revenue from other sources has increased. The consequence has been a decrease in access opportunities for Ugandan youth in the college-age cohort. This has been made worse by the sharp rise in enrollment demand brought on by the larger number of college-age youth who aspire to pursue higher education. Only 5000 Ugandans, or 2% of the country's college-age population, were enrolled in postsecondary institutions in 1970. About 27000 students (8.5%) were enrolled by 1995; over the following decades, this number increased gradually, albeit not always in increments. Enrollment was 137,190 in 2006, or 4.1% of the college-age population. From 1997 to 1986, Uganda experienced years of political unrest that severely disrupted society and undermined the country's educational system. Open To According to Carroll (2005), the recurrent contribution per student fell from \$2,532 in 1970 to \$1,113 in 1980 and \$639 in 1985. Higher education enrollment has increased since 1986. Uganda's gross enrollment ratio (GER) is still less than 5%, which is lower than both the average for the world and the average for sub-Saharan nations. The Ugandan government began to accept private, domestic, and international individuals and organizations to help fund higher education in the late 1980s. Fee-paying students who could afford to pay for their education were allowed to enroll in public universities starting in 1990–1991. The Islamic University, Uganda's first private university, received its license in 1988. The quantity of students who pay fees has exceeded government-sponsored students at public Universities, and there are more private Universities in the nation than public. Studies, however, indicate that rather than solving the issue, private higher education has strengthened unequal access patterns. Students who receive both public and private support typically come from wealthy backgrounds, making it more challenging for underprivileged students to pursue higher education.

3.2. Current Enrolment, Quality, Equity, and Access

3.2.1. Enrollment Rates

According to the latest statistics, Uganda's gross enrollment ratio (GER) in tertiary education increased from 5% in 2000 to around 10% in 2019. This growth indicates improved access for students seeking higher education. Despite the progress, gender disparity remains a concern. Female enrollment rates in higher education still lag, with only 7.1% as compared to 12.3% for males. Efforts are being made to address this imbalance, with scholarships and empowerment programs aimed at encouraging more females to pursue higher education. Access to higher education is often concentrated

in urban areas, creating geographical disparities. Students in rural areas face challenges such as limited infrastructure, lack of qualified teachers, and inadequate resources. The government is working on initiatives to improve facilities and increase opportunities in rural regions.

3.2.2. Education Access and Opportunities in Higher Education in Uganda

The higher education sector in Uganda has evolved to offer a broader range of programs. Traditionally, medical, engineering, and business-related fields dominated, but now there is a growing emphasis on social sciences, humanities, and creative arts. This diversification provides students with more options to explore their interests and talents. Recognizing the importance of vocational skills, Uganda has expanded vocational and technical education opportunities. These programs cater to the needs of students who prefer practical training and are aligned with the country's economic development goals. Vocational training centers and institutes have been set up to equip students with relevant skills. Access to higher education in Uganda has witnessed significant progress in recent years. Efforts have been made to increase enrollment rates and ensure that education becomes accessible to a larger portion of the population. Inclusive policies are essential for providing equal educational opportunities for all individuals. Inclusive policies aim to cater to the diverse needs and aspirations of students, thereby breaking down barriers and ensuring success. According to recent statistics from the Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS), the gross enrollment rate in tertiary education was 6.5% in 2019, compared to 2.5% in 2009. This demonstrates a notable increase in access to higher education opportunities. The government of Uganda in collaboration with various stakeholders, has implemented several measures to enhance accessibility. Initiatives such as the Universal Primary Education (UPE) and Universal Secondary Education (USE) programs have contributed to improved access to primary and secondary education, thereby creating a stronger foundation for students seeking higher education. Affirmative action programs are one example of inclusive policies, as they aim to provide equal opportunities for students from underrepresented backgrounds. For instance, Brazil's quota system in higher education reserves seats for students from low-income families, ethnic minorities, and public school graduates. Enrollment in higher education has increased during the last three decades. The period from the mid-1990s to the early 2000s saw a more notable increase in enrollment, possibly as a result of Makerere University's 1992 introduction of private sponsorship. In actuality, enrollment increased by 12% annually between 1994 and 1999, and Kasozi (2002) predicted a 92% increase in enrollment between 2008 and 2015. In the context of higher education, admission to universities is granted to various student categories. These consist of (a) Government-sponsored students, further classified as talented, disabled, and national merit students; and (b) students admitted through the Inter-University Council for East Africa exchange program for Ugandan universities in Tanzania. Additionally, because of Uganda's growing population, there is a highly competitive loan program for students pursuing higher education. The fields of science and technology and the humanities can be used to stratify the enrollments. Notably, enrollment in the humanities is significantly higher than in the fields of science and technology, with figures for 2010–2011 being 74% and 26%, respectively (NCHE, 2022). Academic staff has become more in demand as a result of new academic programs and universities that have increased enrollment. It should come as no surprise that the majority of highly qualified faculty members at Makerere University hold doctorates; some of them are also professors at private Universities. The limited number of qualified academic staff members bear a heavy workload, which limits the quality of teaching and research due to this stretching of human resource capacity. The regional placement of public Universities and institutions in Uganda, with Mbarara University of Science and Technology established in the west, Gulu University in the north, and Busitema University in the east, is a noteworthy characteristic. This placement was determined by equity and access to higher education. The majority of students who enroll are not always from the corresponding regions because access continues to be determined by merit even with this dispersion. Affirmative action has resulted in additional equity-related changes. Female undergraduate students receive 1.5 bonus points automatically after the regular weight of the points they have earned is determined for their admission portfolios. Their chances of getting admitted are inevitably increased by this bonus. Additionally,

to deal with regional disparities were addressed by assigning student quotas for university admission to different districts (local governing bodies) to improve access, particularly in "disadvantaged" or "hard-to-reach" districts. In terms of enrollment and the number of institutions, Uganda's higher education landscape has never grown larger (Matovu, 2018). Public higher education institutions continue to lead in enrollment even though private higher education has grown significantly. This is partially because private higher education in sub-Saharan Africa is still in its infancy. In Uganda, there are currently more than 50 public and private Universities as well as other institutions that do not grant degrees. Every course in higher education includes instruction in foreign languages, such as Chinese, Arabic, French, and Germans. It is significant to note that the increase in enrollment in public higher education may be partially explained by affirmative action. The demand for PhD holders is another significant development. While it is evident that the number of Ph.D. holders has increased between 2004 and 2011, the need for PhD holders in Uganda will continue to be high due to the significance of research in the country's development (Marginson, 2017). The administration of higher education would be enhanced by systematizing funding, leading to better teaching, research, and community involvement at universities. One could argue that it is essential to set aside special funds for capacity development because Makerere University is the flagship institution and there is a severe shortage of PhD holders (Bisaso, 2018).

3.2.3. Current State of Massification in Higher Education

Massification refers to the rapid expansion of higher education systems to accommodate an increasing number of students. Uganda, like many other developing countries, is experiencing this phenomenon. Massification, or the rapid expansion of higher education, is another significant development in Uganda's higher education landscape. Over the past decade, there has been an increase in the number of universities and tertiary institutions in the country. This expansion is aimed at accommodating the growing demand for higher education. However, the proliferation of institutions has raised concerns about quality control, as not all institutions meet the necessary standards.

To address the quality concerns, Uganda has established the National Council for Higher Education (NCHE). The NCHE oversees the accreditation, regulation, and monitoring of higher education institutions. Quality assurance mechanisms, including curriculum reviews, academic audits, and licensing aim to ensure that institutions maintain the required standards. The government of Uganda offers scholarships to academically gifted but financially disadvantaged students. The Higher Education Students' Financing Board (HESFB) provides loans and grants to deserving students, ensuring that financial constraints do not hinder access to higher education.

According to the Uganda National Council for Higher Education, there are currently 53 universities and other degree-awarding institutions in the country. Despite this apparent progress, the issue of quality assurance and accreditation needs to be addressed to ensure that the degrees obtained from these institutions hold value and provide graduates with the necessary skills for the job market. To address these challenges and promote greater access and opportunities, the Ugandan government and other stakeholders have implemented various initiatives. One such initiative is the introduction of affirmative action policies that aim to increase the enrollment of marginalized groups by providing them with additional support and scholarships. Additionally, there are efforts to improve funding allocation to higher education institutions to enhance infrastructure and resources. Furthermore, partnerships between universities and industries are being established to bridge the gap between academia and the job market. These partnerships help to align educational programs with the needs of the labor market, ensuring that graduates are equipped with the skills and knowledge required for employment. The current statistics shed light on the scale and challenges associated with massification: According to recent statistics, enrollment in Ugandan universities and tertiary institutions has seen a significant upswing over the years. In 2020, the total enrollment in these institutions surpassed 400,000 students, representing a substantial increase compared to the previous decade. The expansion of higher education systems has strained existing infrastructure. Insufficient classrooms, inadequate learning materials, and overcrowded lecture halls pose obstacles to quality education delivery.

The demand for qualified faculty has increased in proportion to student enrollment. However, there is a shortage of qualified educators available to meet this demand, resulting in increased student-teacher ratios and potentially compromising the quality of education. The massification of higher education requires substantial financial resources. The government's ability to invest adequately in infrastructure development, human resources, and research and development remains limited, which impacts the quality of education imparted. Uganda's higher education system faces various challenges related to education access and the ongoing process of massification. While universities and TVET institutions offer opportunities for higher education, socio-economic factors, geographical considerations, and gender disparities continue to impede access. Many studies have demonstrated the link between higher education and economic growth (Philip Altbach et al., 2016). They also noted that expanding access to higher education would be extremely beneficial and that all citizens should pursue it. According to Keith M. Lewin (UNESCO), 2015, higher education has several advantages on the political, social, and economic fronts. It also aids in the development of human capital and professional advancement, fosters knowledge generation through research and innovation, creates equitable opportunities and access, supports lower education levels, fosters connections with the workforce, and fosters international cooperation. Higher education has several positive economic effects, including facilitating employment, enhancing labor mobility, boosting productivity, increasing the demand for skills in knowledge-based economies, promoting employment and development, and raising earnings and savings. Advantages for society of increased enhancement of one's leadership abilities, status, ability to make decisions, and quality of life are all benefits of education. Higher education fosters social cohesion, gender, ethnicity, religion, and greater trust in social institutions and democratic participation. Higher education is essential for developing human capital and professional development since it produces individuals from a wide range of backgrounds, including teachers, physicians, pilots, accountants, researchers, and pilots. The world has changed significantly as a result of technology, human health research, newly invented goods, and agricultural inputs, among other things, thanks to research and innovation produced in higher education institutions. The poor, including women, now have easy access to higher education thanks to the massification of higher education in Africa. It has been observed that postsecondary education fosters international collaboration between academic institutions. As the system experiences significant growth, addressing infrastructure challenges and faculty shortages, and enhancing financial support will be pivotal in maintaining the quality of education offered. The government and relevant stakeholders must work collaboratively to promote inclusive access, improve infrastructure, and ensure adequate funding for higher education in Uganda.

3.3. Challenges of Access and Opportunities in Higher Education in Uganda

Since the beginning of the massification of higher education worldwide, with East Africa and Uganda being particularly affected, the philosophy has faced many difficulties. These difficulties include the inability to meet the rising demands for equity and access, the increased pressure on institutions of higher learning to produce more resources, and the emergence of both competition and corporations in the higher education sector (Welch, 2011). Additional challenges encompass leadership and management, governance, staffing of institutions, relevance and quality of programs, and inadequate research and innovation capacities.

Large class sizes are a hallmark of massification, and this is reflected in both socio-economic development and the standard of instruction and learning received by students. Professors and associate professors are in short supply in Uganda's higher education institutions as Academic staff members with advanced degrees relocate abroad in search of "greener pastures." There are not enough professors in any department at any of Uganda's higher education establishments (NCHE, 2012).

Most Universities use part-time employees because they don't have enough faculty or staff to manage the large number of classes they offer. Staff strikes at public higher education institutions in Uganda are commonplace these days because they are paid inadequate wages for the services they provide (NCHE, 2012).

Duplication of programs, high dropout rates, excessive facility use, a high student-staff ratio, staff inefficiencies, and capacity constraints are all associated with poor leadership, management, and governance in higher education institutions. Because of the massification: poor performance management, financial management, human resource management, partnership development, and strategic planning have all been noted in higher education (Emmanuel, 2016). A nation's socio-economic system is upset by massification. Due to the massification of higher education, there is a high unemployment rate among highly educated individuals. Despite having graduated from college, many people are unemployed.

The skills that graduates possess and the demands of the labor market are not aligned, even with the rise in the number of students enrolling in and graduating from higher education institutions. Employers have frequently lamented that candidates lack the necessary skills in the labor market.

Due to massification, there is an abundance of graduates in certain fields with certain qualifications, flooding the job market. are valued highly in the employment market. This has limited how much money the government spends on education and impacted the standard of instruction provided by the various universities. Declining quality in teaching, research, and community outreach is a challenge that some Ugandan higher education institutions are facing (Marginson, 2017).

Many universities lack proper resources for teaching, including inadequate tools and learning materials, subpar facilities, an unequipped or nonexistent library, and limited access to world knowledge. NCHE has closed Universities or certain university programs as a result of this. The issue of outdated curricula, curricula that place little emphasis on technical skills, and the absence or poor facilitation of institutional, national, and regional quality assurance and enhancement systems are further challenges. Every institution of higher learning lacks the funds necessary to build suitable facilities for the nation's expanding student population. The Ugandan government has cut funding to public Universities while increasing enrollment and refusing to give up control over these institutions of higher learning. To accommodate the high enrollment numbers, facilities in both public and private higher education institutions are completely disorganized (NCHE, 2014). The goal of massification was to establish a framework that would allow everyone in the nation to have access to higher education. However, because of the high cost of higher education, which includes tuition and other expenses that the impoverished cannot afford, this has not been realized to some extent. Because most Ugandans live in poverty and only a small percentage can afford to pay for higher education, this has an impact on the fundamental principles of equity (NCHE, 2012). The massification of higher education has resulted in various issues such as unequal resource distribution, disparities in tuition fees between private and public universities, low enrollment in certain institutions due to competition, and higher education continuing to be primarily accessible to elites from wealthy backgrounds (Hornsby & Osman, 2014).

The number of children who should receive government sponsorship and students who meet the requirements from various families is not governed by any policy (Chou & Wang, 2012). Additional difficulties mentioned are self-awareness, morals, societal shifts, and the goals and objectives of governance and institutions. Notably, the massification of higher education has also resulted in challenges like entrepreneurship surpassing university quality, programs' relevance and connection to industry, and institutions' inability to develop critical thinkers. Major players in higher education have also criticized the system for failing to recognize the importance of education in addressing societal problems like global issues, governance problems, and sustainability problems in development initiatives.

Graduates face challenges in competing for rankings in universities, competitiveness, entrepreneurship and knowledge economy indexes, and University investment ratings, among other factors. The government's attempt to democratize higher education hasn't prevented a mismatch between student enrollment and the number of academic employees, good or poor equipment, and resources that degrade the quality of instruction, research, and community involvement in universities. In Uganda, academic staff growth is at 20% while student growth is at 34.1% (NCHE, 2010). All of the

mentioned factors may be seen in the caliber of graduates, which may then be seen in the advancement of the country.

3.4. Possible Solutions to Education Access, Opportunities, and Massification in Uganda

Encouraging higher education that has been overtaken by massification challenges requires sensible policies to direct the massification process. Rather than social demands being a function of funding or policy, higher education should be guided by government policies (Hui, 2009). To support the large number of students enrolled in higher education institutions, there should be sufficient funding. If the government and other stakeholders don't sufficiently address the problem of funding higher education, it will have an impact on the nation's higher education standards (Marginson, 2017). The nations that have massified higher education around the world have done so by providing generous funding, introducing privatization, offering scholarships, and Students pay tuition to study in higher education institutions through a partnership between the public and private sectors (HESB, 2022). Institutions of higher learning should have a suitable long-term plan, requirements for accepting large numbers of students, and systems in place to keep those numbers high throughout the duration of their studies. In terms of financing, the government ought to provide full funding for postsecondary education in public Universities and encourage private Universities to take the initiative to further the interests of the state (Mohamedbhai, 2008). Families and households ought to be included in the nation's plans for higher education. Because families fund their children's attendance at higher education institutions, household incomes have a direct impact on student enrollment. GDP, or the gross domestic product, and The Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) in higher education institutions are directly impacted by the income levels of the population in a country. The government should assist private higher education institutions by providing tax exemptions, funding for research, and staff salary payments, among other things. According to Los (n.d. 2021), the government cannot establish higher education institutions to educate all of its citizens. The government should set up a favorable environment to draw in foreign higher education institutions in cases where Uganda's private and public higher education institutions are unable to meet the country's demand for education. Reputable Universities from across the globe are free to relocate, even to Uganda, if the circumstances there permit it. Classes in higher education establishments that have accepted massification ought to be divided to provide an adequate number of pupils in lecture halls. Even though increased enrollment benefits society greatly, the caliber of graduates produced as a result of large class sizes shouldn't be compromised. Big classes make it difficult for teachers to deliver their material effectively, which has an impact on students' learning. Courses ought to be divided into manageable groups that lecturers and instructors can effectively oversee. Different cohorts of the same students may be admitted to postsecondary institutions within the same year or during a similar time. Both on and off campus, innovative approaches to teaching large classes are needed. (Osman & Hornsby, 2014) Institutions of higher learning ought to embrace technology to address the problems posed by massification.

With large enrollments in postsecondary education, Off-campus programs like online and distance learning should be offered by universities. This would bring higher education rights to students' doorsteps and ease the congestion in lecture halls at universities and colleges. To admit students, manage their information, provide academic components, and handle all of their affairs, technology should be improved. Students enrolled in specific programs and at higher education institutions should be subject to maximum limits. The National Council for Higher Education ought to conduct a study on the institutional capacity to accept students based on the resources, infrastructure, and facilities that institutions have available to them for admission to specific programs.

Gender parity in admission to postsecondary education should be ensured through massification. The enrollment of females in the number of graduates from higher education increased during the time of national massification of higher education. The government's introduction of 1.5 additional points for female students' admission to public higher education institutions has been largely blamed for the increase in female child admission to higher education institutions. The admissions landscape for female students at public Universities and their enrollment in prestigious programs like

pharmacy, technology, engineering, law, and medicine, among others, have changed as a result of the 1.5 extra point requirements for girl children. When Universities think about massification, they typically think about enrolling more students rather than hiring more academic staff members to teach these students. The scarcity of highly skilled instructors in higher education. Because of the high enrollment in educational institutions, the current staff is required to handle an increased teaching load. Teaching large numbers of students in small classes necessitates grouping the students into smaller groups, which adds to the lecturers' workload. In addition to their heavy workload as lecturers, they also oversee practical lessons, conduct tutorials, administer tests, mark a lot of scripts, and handle administrative duties.

To sustain the high enrollment numbers of students in various programs and the quality of teaching and learning in the face-to-face mode of instruction, massifying higher education would necessitate hiring more permanent academic staff. When taking Uganda's population growth into account, it is expanding very quickly. Since the population is growing so quickly, higher education institutions must be ready to accept these students when the time comes. To accommodate the increasing number of students enrolling in higher education programs, more Universities ought to be founded. To help the overburdened national bodies accredit and oversee quality in the nation's higher education institutions, the government should also require private organizations like ISO 9001 to do the same. They would be responsible for enforcing regulations about student enrollment, and institutional infrastructure, projecting the national human resources needed for higher education institutions to train personnel, and accrediting programs and institutions.

The government should put in place systems in higher education that ensure the majority of its study loans and scholarships go to people who are unable to pay for their tuition. Since the disadvantaged can now more easily pursue higher education, massification will be able to achieve its objective. As massification occurs, comparable programs ought to be implemented concurrently.

To accommodate the large number of students enrolled, programs can be run in multiple cohorts. For instance, students can study online, via distance education, during the day, on weekends, or in the evenings. (Huang et al., 2015) stated that to prepare for post-massification, higher education institutions should manage their affairs, allow market forces to determine the scope, scale, and cost of higher education, and establish both public and private agencies to oversee higher education. Social and economic rationalization should also be reflected in the budget. The post-massification process would entail heightened public awareness, diminished state backing, decreased expenses for tertiary education, competitive and market forces, heightened vocationalization, and extended duration.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

Higher education in Uganda is currently experiencing chaos as it expands beyond what the government can control for a variety of reasons. With its available time, resources, and political will, the Ugandan government must establish the right plans to advance its massification philosophy. Growing massification will probably lead to the creation of global knowledge economies, which will eventually drive national development. The goal of Uganda's higher education massification was to prepare staff members for jobs in the various departments, ministries, and local governments. It's important to recognize that expanding access to higher education through massification aims to close the gap between the impoverished and people from upper social classes. The government should want the nation's higher educational attainment (HEA) and gross enrollment ratio (GER) to be correlated with the massification of higher education. Concerns about quality should arise from massification, as numerous higher education institutions have been founded and are concurrently enrolling sizable student bodies. To accommodate the large number of students, higher education institutions have duplicated courses and lacked adequate equipment. NCHE, 2022 There are a lot of students in lecture halls, and it doesn't seem like their surroundings are conducive to receiving a good education. This has caused the standard of higher education to decline, producing graduates who do not compare to the abilities needed in the labor market. The government should implement strict measures and policies to catch up with higher education institutions that provide education that matches the desired quality in light of massification and the desire for world-class education.

Additionally, as part of the accrediting bodies, the government has given statutory bodies like the Nursing Council, Law Council, and Medical and Dental Practitioners Council the authority to assist in addressing some of the challenges associated with massification in their respective fields. Based on comparative education knowledge, the Chinese educational system was reviewed by Huang et al. (2015) in their review of the country's educational developments over the previous 30 years. To maintain a balance between globalization and localization, centralization and decentralization, top-down and bottom-up, equity-oriented and quality-oriented approaches, policymakers have adopted a balanced and "moderate" approach. Chinese educational systems need to be closely examined for a nation like Uganda to attain equity and access to higher education. Any economy's ability to develop is greatly influenced by its educational system, and the Chinese economy has experienced tremendous growth. While access to education in Uganda is not particularly low, there is still room for improvement in the caliber of graduates. The graduates' unemployment rate is consistent with overpopulation that is not Higher education curricula need to be updated to be in line with existing works so that nearly everyone can enter the market. It is important to thoroughly evaluate graduates' qualities so they can compete in the global market. I have made an effort to shed light on alternative interpretations of China's educational reforms as well as Uganda's educational transformation within various cultural contexts.

Author Contributions: On the first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] AFDB. (2018). African Development Bank Group, Financial highlights Bank Group revenue 2017 and 2018. 70.
- [2] Amutuhaire, T. (2023). IMPROVING ACCESS AND EQUITY IN EAST AFRICAN HIGHER EDUCATION THROUGH. 8(2016), 22-39.
- [3] Bisaso, R. (2018). Makerere University as a Flagship Institution : Sustaining the Quest for Makerere University as a Flagship Institution : Sustaining the Quest for Relevance (Issue June 2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-49403-6>
- [4] Chou, P., & Wang, L.-T. (2012). Who benefits from the massification of higher education in Taiwan? *Chinese Education and Society*, 45, 8-20. <https://doi.org/10.2753/CED1061-1932450501>
- [5] Deutsch, F., Gaunt, R., Murphy-Graham, E., Stojanović, M., Nentwich, J., Schälin, S., Tennhoff, W., Haas, L., Stanley-Stevens†, L., Kusujarti, S., Sikic, L., Roder, D., Choden, T., Takács, J., Márquez, A., Dessen, M., Torres, C., Rose, J., Baxter, J., & Knudson-Martin, C. (2020). Creating Equality at Home: How 25 Couples around the World Share Housework and Childcare. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108597319>
- [6] Dworkin, R. (2021). What is Equality? Part 1: Equality of Welfare. *The Notion of Equality*, 10(3), 81-142. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315199795-6>

- [7] Emmanuel, B. (2016). Does Access to Higher Education for Youth Enhance Sustainable Development in Africa? Some Empirical Lessons from Kogi State, Nigeria. 1(1), 71–95.
- [8] GoU. (1995). The Constitution for the Republic of Uganda. GoU, v. [http://www.cssr.uct.ac.za/sites/cssr.uct.ac.za/files/Constitution Uganda.pdf](http://www.cssr.uct.ac.za/sites/cssr.uct.ac.za/files/Constitution%20Uganda.pdf)
- [9] HESB. (2022). Higher Education in Southeast Asia and Beyond. 11.
- [10] Hornsby, D., & Osman, R. (2014). Massification in higher education: Large classes and student learning. *Higher Education*, 67, 711–719. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-014-9733-1>
- [11] Huang, Z., Wang, T., & Li, X. (2015). The political dynamics of educational changes in China. *Policy Futures in Education*, 14(1), 24–41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1478210315612644>
- [12] Hui, X. De. (2009). Curriculum Reform in the Context of Massification in China.
- [13] Intemann, K. (2010). 25 Years of Feminist Empiricism and Standpoint Theory: Where Are We Now? *Hypatia*, 25(4), 778–796. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1527-2001.2010.01138.x>
- [14] Kasirye Ibrahim. (2009). Determinants of learning achievement in Uganda. Economic Policy Research Centre. October.
- [15] Keith M.Lewin (UNESCO). (2015). Fundamentals of Educational Planning.
- [16] Kotecha, P. (2012). Higher Education in the Southern African Region: Current Trends, challenges, and Recommendations A contribution to the development of a regional strategic plan for revitalizing and strengthening higher education in the SADC region. June.
- [17] Los, U. M. D. E. C. D. E. (n.d.). THE STATE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN SOUTHEAST ASIA.
- [18] Marginson, S. (2017). Higher education, economic inequality, and social mobility: Implications for emerging East Asia. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2017.03.002>
- [19] Marginson, S. (2020). Encyclopedia of International Higher Education Systems and Institutions. *Encyclopedia of International Higher Education Systems and Institutions*, 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-9553-1>
- [20] Matovu, A. P. D. M. (2018). Massification or Quality of Graduates? A Model for Higher Education and Development in Uganda.
- [21] Mohamedbhai, G. (2008). The Role of Higher Education for Human and Social Development in Sub-Saharan Africa (pp. 191–210). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-58169-6_10
- [22] NCHE. (2012). NCHE annual report, equitable access to quality higher education.
- [23] NCHE. (2022). The Uganda Higher Education Review. *Journal of the National Council for Higher Education*, 8(1), 1–69.
- [24] Noui, R. (2020). Higher education between massification and quality. *Higher Education Evaluation and Development*, 14(2), 93–103. <https://doi.org/10.1108/heed-04-2020-0008>
- [25] Owuor, N. (2012). Higher Education in Kenya: The Rising Tension between Quantity and Quality in the Post-Massification Period. *Higher Education Studies*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v2n4p126>
- [26] Philip Altbach e tal, H. (2016). What’s new in higher education? Southeast Asia and Beyond MD s Message. *Higher Education Southeast Asia*, July.
- [27] Sekaggya-Bagarukayo, D., & Oddy, J. (2022). Opportunities and challenges to support out-of-school children and youth through accelerated learning programs: Case study of Uganda. May. <https://inee.org/evidence/e-cubed>.

- [28] Shan, H., & Guo, S. (2014). Massification of Chinese Higher Education (pp. 9–23). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6209-533-5_2
- [29] Thomas, V., Wang, Y., & Fan, X. (2001). VPs 2525. January.
- [30] Trow, M. (2006). Reflections on the Transition from Elite to Mass to Universal Access: Forms and Phases of Higher Education in Modern Societies since WWII (pp. 243–280). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-4012-2_13
- [31] UDHR. (2011). Udhr. Encyclopedia of Global Justice, 1102–1102. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-9160-5_1049
- [32] UN. (2015). Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.
- [33] UNESCO. (2000). The Dakar Framework for Action. Unesco, April, 26–28. <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0012/001211/121147e.pdf>
- [34] UNESCO. (2022). Non-state actors in education. In Global Education Monitoring Report. https://en.unesco.org/gem-report/non-state_actors
- [35] Verspoor, A. (2020). Choices for Secondary Education At the Crossroads.
- [36] World Bank. (2006). World Development Report: Equity and Development. In World Development Report.
- [37] Андрей, С. (2017). Massification of the Higher Education as a Way to Individual Subjective Wellbeing. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2017.01.35>

Authors

Kidega Charles¹,
BAED (Economics and Geography) Kyambogo University, Uganda
M. Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, China.
Email: kidega92@gmail.com

Haufiku Gottlieb Ndambo Djaya
BSc. Education, Namibia
M. Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, China.
cottyfortunecotty@gmail.com

Mintamir Shegaw Taye

B. Management, Rift Valley University, Ethiopia

M. Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, China.

Email: mintamirshegaw2022@gmail.com

Olusegun Adeola Olubunmi

B. Mass Communication, Kogi State University, Nigeria

M. Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, China.

adeolaolusegun@gmail.com

Wakshuma Dime Rare

B. Natural Resource Management, Jimma University College of Agricultural and Veterinary Medicine, Ethiopia

M. Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, China.

wakshumadime@gmail.com

Chirembe Eunifer

B.ED, Midlands University, Zimbabwe

M. Comparative Education. Zhejiang Normal University, China.

euniferc@gmail.com

Awila George

B.ED, Makerere University, Uganda

M. Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, China.

Email: awilageorge12@gmail.com

Thet Khaing

M. Comparative Education

Zhejiang Normal University, China.

College of Education

thetkhaing391@gmail.com